

The Wizard Apprentice: A Serious Games System in Immersive VR as a Feasible Rehabilitation Approach in Children With Cerebral Palsy

Cristian Camardella, Federica Serra¹, Caterina Linciano, Chiara Malasoma, Gabriele Carrieri², Sara Aliboni, Ilaria Bortone, Federico Posteraro, Luca Bonfiglio³, and Daniele Leonardis⁴

Abstract—Virtual reality offers the opportunity to engage the participant in challenging rehabilitation exercises, proposed in the shape of serious games. Modern VR technologies can further enhance usability, allowing the participant to seamlessly interact with VR environment with bare hands, without need of external tracking systems and complex setups. In children neurorehabilitation engagement can promote motivation and attention to the exercise, two key elements for effectiveness of the rehabilitation process. In this work we developed a rehabilitation system composed of three serious games in immersive VR, with motor exercises targeting the upper limb and trunk in children with Cerebral Palsy. The participant plays in the role of a wizard apprentice, called to cast spells, to prepare potions and to ride a magic eagle. These game scenarios involve coordinated motor functions related to trajectory tracking, pick-and-place with prono-supination, and trunk balance. The presented pilot study (12 CP children, 24 sessions), focuses on the feasibility assessment of the rehabilitation method, then, it allows a more in depth analysis on the adaptation and progress of the exercise parameters through data recorded during the whole treatment. The study shows that immersive VR games are a feasible approach in rehabilitation procedures, with positive results regarding acceptability, retention, adherence to the planned exercises and absence of adverse effects in the long-term use. They also show promising results in

improvements of motor functions, although a direct comparison with a control group was not included in the study.

Index Terms—Rehabilitation, immersive, virtual reality, serious games, cerebral palsy, haptics, wearable.

I. INTRODUCTION

CHRONIC neuromotor disorders affect a wide range of pediatric neurological conditions that cause significant limitations in daily activities [1]. Among these disorders is Cerebral Palsy (CP) which comprises a group of pathologies that alter motor control and posture due to non-progressive damage to the developing central nervous system. This neurological disorder is the leading cause of motor disability in childhood (prevalence in Europe: 1.77/1,000 per year [2]) and can coincide with alterations in sensation, cognition, communication, perception and can lead to seizure disorders. CP is often characterized by impairment of the upper limbs, and therefore rehabilitation programs play a key role in improving and maximizing the function of the affected limbs and promoting independence in daily activities [3], [4].

To help people with CP achieve their functional goals, users are often subjected to conventional therapies, such as physical or occupational therapy [5], [6], [7]. While efficacy of conventional methods is well established, novel approaches show the potential to improve repeatability, quantitative measurements of patient's progress [8], [9]. Moreover, the serious games approach can improve involvement of the user in otherwise repetitive motor tasks [10].

More recent rehabilitation approaches based on novel technologies can overcome these barriers and improve the overall rehabilitation process. The use of virtual reality (VR) exercises proposed in the shape of serious games, with or without the addition of assistive robotic devices, has emerged as one of the most explored approaches in the last years [11], [12], [13]. Virtual reality proves a powerful tool for shaping goal-oriented motor tasks, offering different advantages: flexibility and parametrization of the exercises, allowing the therapist to modulate the difficulty of the exercise for each participant,

Received 19 January 2025; revised 28 May 2025 and 4 July 2025; accepted 28 July 2025. Date of publication 4 August 2025; date of current version 12 August 2025. This work was supported by the Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Program (Social and hUman ceNtered XR-SUN Project) under Grant 101092612. (Corresponding author: Daniele Leonardis.)

This work involved human subjects in its research. Approval of all ethical and experimental procedures and protocols was granted by the Meyer Hospital (Florence, Italy), under Application No. 221-2021.

Cristian Camardella, Federica Serra, and Daniele Leonardis are with the Department of Excellence in Robotics and AI and the Institute of Mechanical Intelligence, Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna, 56127 Pisa, Italy (e-mail: c.camardella@santannapisa.it; d.leonardis@santannapisa.it).

Caterina Linciano, Gabriele Carrieri, and Luca Bonfiglio are with the University Hospital of Pisa (AOUH), 56126 Pisa, Italy.

Chiara Malasoma, Sara Aliboni, and Federico Posteraro are with the Azienda USL Toscana Nord Ovest (ATNO), 56121 Pisa, Italy.

Ilaria Bortone is with the Italian National Research Council (CNR), 56124 Pisa, Italy.

Digital Object Identifier 10.1109/TNSRE.2025.3595420

the intrinsic ability of these VR systems to continuously record quantitative kinematic data, and repeatability of the treatment. These aspects together provide better conditions for fine-analysis of the participant's progress, and therefore potential for better adaptation of the therapy to participant's needs. Yet another very important advantage is found in the gaming approach followed by many of these virtual rehabilitation methods [14]. Gamification of the rehabilitation exercise is expected to foster participant's engagement and her/his motivation to improve performance, which is a crucial aspect in neuro-rehabilitation, considering that active mental participation is an undeniable factor to promote brain plasticity and, thus, boost motor recovery [15].

To enhance immersion and congruence of the provided visual feedback, haptic feedback has been explored in the rehabilitation field, although typically still limited to vibratory feedback informative of hand interactions [16], [17], [18] or providing event-related postural information [19], especially in lower limb and gait rehabilitation exercises [20]. We explored in previous studies the integration of wearable haptic devices in VR rehabilitation settings [21], and we include in the presented work novel, more compact devices designed for compliance with vision-based hand tracking [22], [23].

Immersive virtual rehabilitation systems are increasingly explored in neurological rehabilitation [24]. These systems offer a twofold advantage: enhanced immersivity, which may lead to greater user engagement, and improved congruency of visual feedback, providing a direct correspondence between the user's physical body and the virtual body representation. VR approaches tailored to pediatric populations remain relatively scarce and often fragmented. As outlined in Table I, many studies involving children with cerebral palsy (CP) have focused on short-term feasibility, proof-of-concept designs, or non-immersive desktop-based setups [25], [26], [27], [28]. Only a few studies, such as [21] and [29], have explored the potential of immersive VR in combination with wearable haptic feedback; others employed immersive VR in larger clinical groups, with exercises focused on trunk balance [30], [31].

The present study responds to these gaps by proposing and testing a fully immersive VR rehabilitation system including wearable haptic devices. The system is evaluated in a long-term, clinically supervised protocol targeting upper limb and trunk control in children with CP. This feasibility study aims to demonstrate the clinical usability, engagement potential, and capacity for quantitative tracking within an immersive, game-based rehabilitation framework.

The study further extend our previous work [21], [29] experimenting three novel serious games scenarios based on the latest VR technologies, focusing on upper-limb and trunk balance exercises. The above advances leverage usability of the system by non-technical clinical personnel, and the quality and richness of the experience proposed to the participants.

The paper is structured as follows: Section II describes the three virtual scenarios and the haptic devices; Section III reports the study participants, the clinical assessment performed and a description of the parameters varied by the therapist and game metrics recorded for each virtual scenario.

TABLE I

SUMMARY OF SELECTED STUDIES ON IMMERSIVE OR VR-BASED REHABILITATION IN CHILDREN WITH CEREBRAL PALSY

Study	Population	VR Setup	N. Sess.	Clinical Setting
[21]	CP, n=8	Immersive VR + haptics	16	Yes
[29]	CP, n=6	Immersive VR + haptics	1	Yes
[30]	CP + Brain injury, n=80	Desktop-based VR	20	Yes
[25]	CP, n=24	Desktop VR + EMG biofeedback	12	Yes
[26]	CP, n=20	VR + EMG biofeedback	1	Yes
[27]	CP, n=16	Immersive treadmill (GRAIL) + biofeedback	1	No
[28]	CP / UL impairment, n=3	Desktop VR + EMG + IMU	16	No
[32]	CP, n=10	Desktop Kinect-based VR	12	Yes
[31]	CP, n=17	Immersive VR	16	Yes

Section IV reports the results obtained and Section V the discussions and final conclusions.

II. SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

The proposed system is composed of three serious games scenarios provided to the participant by means of a Meta Quest 2 VR headset, used in stand-alone mode. The headset features embedded head and hands tracking, which is exploited by the virtual exercises implementation. Compact and lightweight haptic devices, worn at the fingertips, are used to convey tactile events in the first two upper-limb exercises. Differently, a waist-band equipped with a wireless inertial measurement unit (IMU) is used for the third trunk-balance exercise. No other tracking or wearable devices, further than the headset and either the haptic or IMU device, are needed to be worn by the patient. At the therapist side, a wide monitor is used to visualize the VR environment outside the headset. A Graphical User Interface (GUI) is also provided through a laptop PC to control the exercise status and parameters. Data measured within the VR application are sent in real-time via WiFi (UDP communication) from the headset to the host PC, where they are stored together with the GUI parameters.

A. Design and Structure of the Virtual Serious Games

Three virtual gaming scenarios have been developed using Unity, involving upper limb and trunk balance rehabilitation exercises. The recruited motor functions and the game logic have been developed by a mixed team of technical and clinician researchers. The first scenario includes a highly generalizable pick-and-place task with pronosupination, which is involved in many Activities of Daily Living (ADLs). The second scenario focuses on higher precision and multi-joint coordination of the upper limb. Hence, it includes a path tracking task with a final aiming and launching phase, requiring both precise upper-limb coordination to accomplish

Fig. 1. a) Sequence of the motor task b) Task representation in the game scenario c) The haptic devices and the VR headset are worn by the child during therapy. d) Grasping phase e) Reaching phase. f) Pouring phase. g) Releasing phase.

the trajectory-following task. These exercises involved one hand only (selectable between left or right). For children with hemiplegia, exercises were always played with the affected hand, while, for children with diplegia, it was played with the hand more needed to foster autonomy. The third scenario involves trunk balancing, and served also as a break in-between upper-limb exercises. In the game setting, the child takes the role of a wizard apprentice, involved in preparing potions, launching spells, and riding a magic eagle.

1) *Virtual Scenario 1: Potions Class*: In the scenario the child has to learn how to prepare a magic potion, in an environment immersed in ancient books, cauldrons and magical ingredients. As part of this interactive game, the child is asked to assume the role of an apprentice magician, tasked with preparing a magical potion by mixing various ingredients in a cauldron (Fig. 1). The child is involved in pick-and-place motor tasks including prono-supination, in order to grasp the right ingredient from a shelf, and to pour the right amount of the ingredient into a cauldron. Cognitive elements are introduced to increase the child's interest and motivation by requiring accuracy in the amount of liquid poured into the cauldron. A green reference line on a progress bar indicates the ideal amount of liquid to pour.

2) *Virtual Scenario 1: Potions Class*: In the scenario the child has to learn how to prepare a magic potion, within an environment immersed in ancient books, cauldrons and magical ingredients (Fig. 1). The exercise is composed of a pick-and-place motor tasks including prono-supination, in order to grasp the right ingredient from a shelf, and to pour the required amount into a cauldron.

The game phases of the Potions Class scenario are:

- **a) Grasping:** a red arrow suggests to the child the ingredient to take from among the various bottles on a table. The child grasps the ingredient by performing a pinching action with the hand.
- **b) Reaching:** the child brings the ingredient on top of the cauldron.
- **c) Pouring:** the child starts pouring by rotating the ingredient over the given angular threshold, and stops the

pouring by rotating back the bottle below the angular threshold. A progress bar indicates the ideal amount of liquid to pour.

- **d) Releasing:** The child places and releases the ingredient at the initial location on the shelf.

To complete the potion, the cycle is repeated for five ingredients, all forming a gaming round. At the end, if the potion has been correctly prepared, a green smoke emerges from the cauldron and a magical animal appears in reward nearby the child. Otherwise, a black smoke emerges from the cauldron and no animal appears.

The therapist could parameterize the exercise by varying the difficulty of the recipes, determined by the placement of the ingredients within the workspace, the speed and precision required to pour the ingredients, and the minimum pronation angle necessary to start the pouring action.

Regarding haptic feedback, it conveys normal forces at fingerpads congruently to the grasping transition. During the pouring phase, a modulated vibration is added, synchronized with the sound of a flowing liquid.

3) *Virtual Scenario 2: Spell Cast*: In the Spell Cast scenario the child has to learn how to cast powerful spells (Fig. 2) by tracing the corresponding magical symbol. Symbols are presented in mid air one at a time and have to be drawn with the index finger by following the visual trace. The drawing accuracy, compared to the shown visual reference, determines the spell's power. After the tracing phase, the spell appears in the hand and has to be aimed and cast against an enemy, appearing in the middle of a magic circle, by following a linear trajectory. Simple cognitive elements are introduced with the aim of stimulating higher involvement in the game. In example, the suggested spells are associated with magical elements (such as Fire, Water, Wind, etc.) and in turn associated to weak points of the presented enemies.

The exercise parametrization includes the difficulty of the prescribed trajectory, through a library of symbols with different complexity, the dimensional scaling of the symbol, the required tracing precision, and the moving velocity of the target enemy.

Fig. 2. Spell Cast scenario and sequence of actions: a) Start tracing b) Symbol tracing c) Spell creation d) Aiming and cast e) Experimental setup.

The game phases of the Spell Cast scenario are:

- **a) Start Tracing:** the hand is either in a point or pinch pose (selectable by the therapist), with such pose held for two seconds at the starting point of the reference symbol, marked by a red circle. Then, a flame appears at the fingertip;
- **b) Tracing:** the symbol is traced following the indicated path.
- **c) Spell Creation:** the hand is opened, and the spell (i.e. a fire ball) is visualized floating in the hand palm;
- **d) Aiming:** by orienting the hand, a violet ray traced from the hand palm has to be pointed towards the enemy.
- **e) Casting:** by performing a linear movement of the hand along the violet aiming line, the spell is launched. A velocity threshold is used to release the spell from the hand.

A full gaming round was composed of a sequence of three enemies to defeat. The Spell Cast environment and game sequence is depicted in Fig. 2. Haptic feedback with vibration components modulated by the tracing velocity is provided during the tracing phase. Different modulated vibrations are provided once the spell floats in the player's hand. A 2D spatial projection and a dynamic time warping (DTW) algorithm is employed to process position tracking data in order to determine the precision score of the symbol in the game logic (Fig. 2).

4) *Virtual Scenario 3: Eagle Ride:* This scenario places the child on the saddle of a magic eagle, flying in a slow-paced and relaxing mountain environment. The exercise is targeted at postural balance, by means of gentle leaning of the trunk in order to guide the trajectory of the eagle. A reference path is defined by a series of waypoints. Different control modalities, described hereafter, can be selected to guide the eagle using the posture of the trunk. If the player deviates from the ideal trajectory, the eagle gradually slows down. This logic makes the game robust to novice players and easier for them to find again the waypoint if it gets out of sight. Also, since the velocity of the eagle is the highest when the waypoint is correctly targeted, it promotes precision of the movement

in order to indirectly increase the velocity of the game. The following control modalities were implemented:

The game modalities of the Eagle Ride scenario are:

- **Automatic mode** - Fully automatic mode, the eagle is automatically guided throughout the waypoints. The option is used the first time to get the child acquainted to the scenario.
- **Roll control mode** - The child is required to gently lean the trunk on the right or on the left, on the sagittal plane, in order to steer the direction of flight. The steering velocity is proportional to the leaning angle of the trunk (roll axis).
- **Roll and Pitch control mode** - Similar to the Roll control mode. In this condition, also the pitch angle of the eagle (up-down direction) has to be modulated by gently leaning the trunk upward and backward in order to reach waypoints at different heights.
- **Free mode** - In this condition the flight trajectory of the eagle is unconstrained even if the eagle gets out of the path. Both roll and pitch angles of the trunk are used to steer the eagle left/right and up/down. Waypoints are the same than in the other conditions.

Moreover, the therapist could parametrize the exercise changing the total number of waypoints in each round, and the scaling of the eagle speed. A full gaming round corresponded to the completion of single path of ten to twenty waypoints, set by the therapist.

B. The Wearable Haptic Interface

Tactile feedback of virtual object interaction has been included by custom developed wearable haptic thimbles. In this study the focus was to increase wearability and compliance of these devices with respect to both participants' comfort and compliance with the embedded hand tracking system provided by the 3D headset. A light and thin haptic thimble has been developed, with direct-drive actuation targeted at rendering low amplitude, yet clean and dynamic pressure signals directly at the fingerpad tissue. These include fast transients, textures and modulated vibrations (Fig. 4).

Fig. 3. a), b): The movements performed by the child atop the eagle to reach the bright targets are the tilting of the torso to the right or left to steer the eagle's flight, and the trunk control to balance and maintain stability during the eagle's flight. c) The Oculus Quest 2 is worn by the child during therapy. d), e): Display of the Eagle Ride VR scenario.

Fig. 4. The thimble wearable haptic device developed for high wearability and compliance with vision-based tracking systems. a) Assembled design and b) section view of the internal voice coil. c) Detail of the soft actuated membrane in blue color. d) Device worn at the hand of a child.

A miniaturized custom-made electromagnetic voice coil (outer diameter 12 mm, output force 0.4 N) was implemented due to the linear output and to the wide frequency response of this type of actuators. The thimble is fabricated in a soft resin, Photocentric Ultraviolet Digital Light Processing (UV DLP) Flexible, making it adaptable to different finger sizes. The weight of each haptic thimble is 7 g, while the weight of the wireless electronics box worn at the forearm, including the battery, is 60g. The large capacity battery (1500 mAh) allows extended operation for about 4-5 hours, depending on the intensity of the haptic events. Further technical details can be found in [22]. The same electronics includes an IMU sensor (InvenSense MPU6050), and is used as a wireless inclinometer, worn at the trunk, for the Eagle Ride scenario.

III. EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

A. Participants

Twelve children (10 male and 2 female) with Cerebral Palsy in its hemiplegic and diplegic forms were recruited for the study. The inclusion criteria were a confirmed diagnosis of CP, with participants aged between 6 and 14 years (Table II). The exclusion criteria were epileptic users, severe deficit in sensory perception of upper limb, severe visual impairments and severe cognitive involvement. All participants provided a

TABLE II
PARTICIPANTS

Sbj	Age	Gender	CP type	Etiology	GMFCS	MACS	Game
1	7.0	Male	Hemiplegic (L)	Perinatal stroke	I	II	1-3
2	6.0	Male	Diplegic	Hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy	I	I	1-3
3	9.0	Male	Hemiplegic (L)	Perinatal stroke	I	I	1-3
4	6.0	Male	Hemiplegic (R)	Perinatal stroke	I	II	1-3
5	14.0	Female	Hemiplegic (L)	Perinatal stroke	II	II	1-3
6	12.0	Male	Hemiplegic (L)	Paediatric stroke	I	I	1-3
7	13.0	Male	Diplegic	Hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy	IV	III	1-3
8	12.0	Male	Hemiplegic (L)	Perinatal stroke	II	II	1-3
9	7.0	Male	Bilateral hemiparesis	Hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy	I	II	1-3
10	9.0	Male	Hemiplegic (R)	Perinatal stroke	I	II	1-3
11	6.0	Female	Hemiplegic (R)	Perinatal stroke	I	II	1-3
12	9.0	Male	Hemiplegic (L)	Perinatal stroke	I	III	1-3

minimum ability to actively use their upper limb and understand simple instructions. The parents or legal guardians of the children provided written informed consent for participation. The clinical study was approved by the pediatric ethical committee of the Meyer hospital (Florence, Italy) with protocol number 221-2021.

B. Clinical Assessments

Clinical assessment was performed at the beginning (Time T0) and at the end (Time T1) of the therapy, using the following scales: the Box and Block Test (BBT) [33], the Nine Hole Peg Test (NHPT) [34], the Time Up and Go (TUG) [35], the Melbourne Assessment 2 (MA2) sub-divided in the range of motion, precision, dexterity and smoothness scores.

C. Measured Data

The following criteria were adopted to conduct the feasibility study:

- **Retention** - Ability to complete treatment
- **Adherence** - Consistency and intensity of the treatment
- **Acceptability** - Acceptability and occurrence of adverse effects
- **Usability** - Usability of the system and occurrence of technical issues.

Moreover, we analyzed two data sources: the game parameters set for each session, adapted by the therapist on the

TABLE III
PARAMETERS SET BY THE THERAPIST AND MEASURED METRICS

Scenario	Parameter	Description
Potions	Workspace Level	Difficulty of the recipe based on placement of ingredients within the upper limb workspace. Fifteen recipes increase difficulty by combining ipsi- to contra-lateral and lower to higher shelf placements.
Potions	Pouring Velocity	Quantity poured per second; higher speed requires faster pronation and supination to pour the required amount.
Potions	Pouring Precision	Precision needed for poured quantity to prepare the potion correctly; higher values mean harder exercises.
Potions	Pouring Angle	Minimum pronation angle to start pouring, normalized 0–1 equals 30 deg to 90 deg.
Spells	Tracing Precision	Precision threshold at the end of symbol tracing phase, to generate the spell.
Spells	Symbol Dimension	Dimension of the symbol to trace, the normalized range corresponds to a minimum dimension of 0.25 m to the maximum dimension of 1 m.
Spells	Symbol Level	Complexity of the symbol to be traced. A set of 16 symbols with increasing shape complexity was prepared and selected at the beginning of each session.
Spells	Target Velocity	Speed of the target enemy to aim and hit during casting.
Eagle Ride	Speed Level	Global speed scaling of the eagle. Actual velocity is also modulated during the game by current heading precision toward the next waypoint.
Eagle Ride	Pitch Control Enabled	If enabled, the game requires to modulate also the pitch angle by leaning the trunk forward and backward. If disabled, this angle is automatically adjusted by the eagle based on the height of the next waypoint.
Eagle Ride	Free Flight Enabled	If enabled, the eagle can be guided without path constraints (i.e. velocity gradually reduced to zero when heading angle is over 60 deg error). Reserved to more expert players.

Scenario	Metric	Description
Potions	Completion Time	Elapsed time in seconds for completing each ingredient.
Potions	Hand Rotation	Mean hand rotation with respect to the initial hand orientation, recorded at the grasping event of each ingredient.
Potions	Fallen Objects	Number of objects fallen from the virtual grasping, averaged for each session.
Potions	Precision Score	Average score assigned by the game for the completion of each ingredient, based on the measured error between the poured quantity of the ingredient and the reference quantity.
Spells	Tracing Velocity	Mean tracing velocity measured at the index finger of the active hand during the symbol tracing phase.
Spells	Tracing Smoothness	Smoothness index computed as the averaged absolute acceleration measured during the symbol tracing phase.
Spells	Aiming Time	Time elapsed in seconds between the end of the tracing phase and the cast of the spell.
Spells	Aiming Precision	Angle in degrees between the aiming trajectory (shown to the participant as a purple line normal to the hand's palm) and the target enemy.
Eagle Ride	Heading Error	Average error angle in degrees between the heading direction of the eagle and the direction of the next waypoint.
Eagle Ride	Velocity	Averaged speed of the eagle: it is at the maximum value when the heading error angle is zero, while it is diminished when the heading error increases (zero velocity at heading error equal to 60 deg).

basis of the progress of the participant, and the game metrics, which include kinematic data and other exercise-specific measurements. Parameters and metrics for each scenario are described in Table III. In the plotted results the parameters are normalized in the range 0 - 1, corresponding to the minimum and maximum value ever set in any session and for any participant.

A 5 points Likert scale questionnaire was collected after the treatment from parents of the children. Table IV shows all the questions, related to acceptability of the proposed therapy.

D. Statistical Analysis

The objectives of the statistical analysis were: a) to assess a statistical significant difference on clinical scale scores, between t_0 and t_1 ; b) assess a statistical difference between game parameters set by therapist between t_0 and t_1 ; c) assess a statistical difference between game performance indexes between t_0 and t_1 . Given the limited sample size and the absence of normality, non-parametric tests only were run.

TABLE IV
ACCEPTABILITY QUESTIONNAIRE

Q	Questions
Q1	The child appreciated the proposed rehabilitation treatment.
Q2	The child was engaged and committed throughout the rehabilitation treatment.
Q3	The child had fun during the rehabilitation sessions.
Q4	The exercises proposed during the rehabilitation treatment were easy to understand and perform.
Q5	The child felt comfortable wearing the necessary devices for the rehabilitation treatment.
Q6	I am satisfied with the results achieved by my child.

Wilcoxon signed rank paired tests were used to assess the difference among the two conditions, being the two groups dependent variables. The significance levels on the p-value have been set to 0.05, 0.01, and 0.001 corresponding to one, two, or three asterisks in the following plots.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Measurement of the feasibility criteria obtained the following results:

TABLE V
AVERAGE GAMING ROUNDS PER REHABILITATION SESSION

	Potions	Spells	Eagle	All
Round. per day	3.3 ± 0.8	2.9 ± 0.85	3.0 ± 1.0	9.3 ± 1.4

Fig. 5. Boxplots illustrating the distribution of responses to the six Likert scale items listed in Table IV.

Retention - All the patients were able to complete the proposed protocol.

Adherence - The administered exercise intensity, reported in Table V, showed balanced intensity for the three scenarios. Considering the total number of gaming rounds per day, the measured value is 9.3 ± 1.4 , showing a relatively limited inter-subject deviation from the average. Each gaming round refer to the completion of either one potions, (duration of about 4 minutes). This should not be mistaken for the exercise sessions per day, which refers to the total number of all game instances.

Usability - The system could be operated by clinical personnel alone, with technical personnel present during the first rehabilitation session of each new patient. Technical interventions during the therapy were limited to the following: extensions of parameters' range on the basis of the first day of therapy; added an optional, different starting hand pose for casting spells; added the free-flight condition, added additional rewards in the Potions Class scenario, added new spells and enemies in the Spell Cast scenario. Minor interventions were performed throughout the therapy (less than 10 for hospital) related to network connection issues, setting of the workspace, software updates required by the headset.

Acceptability - The responses to the Likert scale questionnaire, collected after the treatment from parents of the children, reported noticeably high scores to all the questions as shown in Figure 5). No adverse effects were recorded during the treatment.

Results of the assessment using clinical scales at the beginning and at the end of the treatment is reported in Fig.6. All the adopted scales show a trend of the median value according to an improvement of motor outcomes at the end of the therapy. Significant differences are found for the BBT score (mean Start: 19.0, End: 24.4, $p < 0.01$), for the MA2 ROM (mean Start: 0.72, End: 0.80, $p < 0.01$), for the MA2 Dexterity (mean Start: 0.65 End: 0.74, $p < 0.01$) and for the MA2 Smoothness (mean Start: 0.71 End: 0.78, $p < 0.01$). Regarding the NHPT, 4 participants were not able to accomplish the test. Similarly 2 patients were not able to accomplish the TUG test. These participants were excluded from the statistical analysis of the corresponding clinical scale.

Game parameters results are reported for each scenario using barplots comparing the initial set of values, chosen by the therapist for each participant at the beginning of the therapy, and the last set of values set at the end of the therapy.

Game metrics results are plotted over the percentage of accomplished rehabilitation treatment (considering the number of performed sessions rather than date and time) for each children, taking into account minor discrepancies from the total number of sessions.

Barplots in Fig. 7 show results of the parameters set by the therapist for the Potions Scenario, normalized in the 0-1 range. All the parameters show a trend of increasing difficulty between the start and the end of the therapy, except the Pouring Angle threshold holding the same mean value. The Pouring Velocity shows a marked difference with statistical significance (median value Start: 0.06, End: 0.74, $p < 0.01$). Regarding the measured metrics in the Potions scenario (Fig. 7), the Completion Time shows a difference with statistical significance (mean Start: 21.6, End: 14.17, $p < 0.01$). The Completion Time and the Fallen Objects metrics show an evident trend according to an improvement in performance during therapy. Both metrics show a similar oscillatory behavior; such similarity can be explained by the relation between the two metrics, with a higher number of grasping attempts corresponding to a higher Completion Time. The Precision Score shows only a slight, yet not marked improvement (mean Start: 0.98, End: 1.03). The Hand Rotation Angle also does not show a noticeable variation throughout the therapy (mean Start: 65.5 deg End: 64.3 deg). This is in agreement with the almost constant parameter set for the pouring angle, close to 80 deg, and considering that the mean value of the measured angle includes also the transient phases of the whole pronation-supination action.

For the Spells Scenario, the serious game parameters shown in Fig. 8 result in a noticeable variation for the Symbol Complexity Level (median Start: 0.15, End: 0.97, $p < 0.001$), and for the Target Velocity (median Start: 0.0, End: 0.71, $p < 0.05$). The Symbol Dimension did not show a change from the median value (0.5, corresponding to 0.5 meters). Regarding the measured metrics in the Spells Scenario (Fig. 8), the Tracing Velocity did not show marked variations throughout the therapy (mean Start: 0.91, End: 1.04). The normalized Smoothness metric, computed on the traced trajectory, shows a significant difference (mean Start: 0.91 End: 1.16, $p < 0.05$). Metrics of the aiming and launching phases show again a constant trend for the Aiming Time (mean Start: 11.14 s, End: 10.3 s), and a slight, not significant decrease of the Aiming Error (mean Start: 19.78 deg, End: 18.74 deg). Results of the above measured metrics should be considered together with the increased difficulty of the exercises, shown by the barplot in the same Fig. 8, and discussed more in details in the next section.

Finally, parameters recorded for the the Eagle Ride Scenario are depicted in Fig. 9. Significant increments from the start to the final settings are found for the Speed Level (median Start: 0.88, End: 1, $p < 0.05$) and for the Pitch Enabled parameters (median Start: 0.0, End: 0.5, $p < 0.05$). The Free Flight modality changed from 0.17 to 0.42, with 5 over

Fig. 6. Summary of clinical scale scores for all the children with cerebral palsy. Each boxplot shows the distribution of each variable, having the whiskers that show the 1st and 4th quartiles, the blue box that shows the 2nd and 3rd quartile, and the red line that shows the median. Red crosses are outliers. One, two or three black asterisks show the significance level with p-value respectively lower than 0.05, 0.01, and 0.001. All adopted clinical scales show a median value trend consistent with motor improvement at the end of the therapy.

Fig. 7. Results of the Potions Scenario. Boxplot shows the starting and ending values of parameters set by the therapist, ranging from 0 to 1; higher values correspond to increased task difficulty. The progress plots show the average metrics over the percentage of completion of the therapy. Performance improvements correspond to higher values, except for the Fallen Objects and Completion Time, which improve with decreasing values.

12 participants experiencing the more advanced exercise feature at the end of the treatment. Measured metrics show a marked difference with statistical significance for the Heading Error (mean Start: 26 deg, End: 16 deg, $p < 0.05$) and for the Eagle Velocity (normalized mean value Start: 0.75, End: 1.18, $p < 0.05$).

Fig. 8. Results of the Spells Scenario. Boxplot shows the starting and ending values of parameters set by the therapist, ranging from 0 to 1; higher values correspond to increased task difficulty. The progress plots show the average variation of the recorded metrics with respect to the percentage of completion of the therapy. Performance improvement corresponds to an increase of the metric values, except for Aiming Time and Aiming Error, which improve as their values decrease.

V. DISCUSSIONS

A. Feasibility Assessment

The aim of this study was to experiment the feasibility of an immersive VR rehabilitation setup in a prolonged clinical rehabilitation treatment. Regarding the retention criteria, all the children were able to complete the rehabilitation treatment,

Fig. 9. Results of the Eagle Scenario. Boxplot shows the starting and ending values of parameters set by the therapist, ranging from 0 to 1; higher values correspond to increased task difficulty. The progress plots show the average variation of the recorded metrics with respect to the percentage of completion of the therapy. Performance improvement is reflected in a decrease in Heading Error and an increase in Velocity.

supporting the adopted protocol and the inclusion criteria. Only one child declined to participate to the study, and refused to try the VR headset due to tactile hypersensitivity in the head area. Positive results were recorded in terms of adherence to the therapy intensity, showing a limited inter-subject variation from the average, and showing the adaptability of the exercise difficulty to the different patients.

Acceptability was notably high, with no adverse effects recorded throughout the therapy. We highlight that the use of the system was cautious, with numerous short breaks (1-2 minutes every 5-10 minutes of exercise) performed without the headset. The serious games approach obtained engagement of the participants, as noted by direct therapist observations. The final acceptability questionnaire, answered by parents, reported high scores for all the participants. This result has to be cautiously considered, taking into account the positive expectations that a novel medical technology might arise in the general public, which might have boosted the responses. Still, the results support the acceptability of similar procedures by the end users. Usability of the virtual scenarios was positively validated, with the clinical staff operating the system independently throughout the therapy. Technical staff supervised only the first rehabilitation session for each new participant and intervened occasionally for the technical issues enlisted in the Results section. Remarkably, one of the key advantages of the recent VR headsets is the integrated tracking system, which significantly simplifies the calibration process and improves robustness of the setup. Parametrization of the exercises was a crucial and demanding phase of the system development, requiring continuous interactions between

developers and tests with clinical personnel. However, not all the parameters exposed in the GUI were varied in the end as expected, suggesting that a more refined selection could enhance system usability. As regards the haptic feedback, the study shows it can be introduced without affecting usability and acceptability of the overall system. The thimble prototypes proved robust to a relatively high number of sessions, although the soft body of the thimbles was replaced once for device. Haptic feedback contributed to the overall immersion and congruency of the sensory feedback provided to the participants, still its specific role cannot be evaluated given the presented experimental setup.

B. Clinical Observations

The statistically significant result obtained in the BBT indicates an improvement in the manual skills of cluster grasping, holding, transferring, and releasing objects, all useful skills for carrying out many activities of daily living. This improvement is consistent with tasks that were specifically trained by gaming scenarios and that required both proximal and distal upper limb movements, but did not involve finer digital manipulation skills (such as pincer grasp). Previous studies have defined the MCID for the BBT in children with CP as 6-7 blocks [33], hence the observed increase of approximately 8 blocks indicates clinical relevance of the improvements in gross manual dexterity.

Regarding the Melbourne Assessment 2 (MA2), our study showed significant improvements in range of motion, dexterity, and smoothness. These domains correspond closely to upper limb coordination and movement quality, outcomes that have also been reported in prior VR-based interventions, including those using desktop systems or semi-immersive feedback [11], [12]. According to Wang et al. [36], the MCID thresholds for these subdomains are 2.35 (ROM), 2.22 (Dexterity), and 3.20 (Fluency/Smoothness). The magnitude of score shifts observed in our study meets or surpasses these thresholds, suggesting that change are clinically meaningful. In contrast, the Precision MA2 parameter and the Nine Hole Peg Test (NHPT), which assesses fine finger dexterity, did not change significantly. This is consistent with prior studies reporting limited NHPT gains unless the intervention specifically targets digital motor control. Still, the average NHPT improvement was in line with the MCID reported by Carey et al. on the same population [37].

Regarding the trunk balance exercise, the discrepancy between the results of the TUG and the Heading Error and Velocity metrics of Eagle Ride Scenario is likely to be found in the fact that in the evaluation of the former, dynamics of walking and postural transitions have a meaningful weight, thus providing an indirect and non-specific evaluation of balance, whereas metrics relating to Eagle Scenario provide a measure of the skills specifically trained in the game (i.e., the ability to control trunk movements and to distribute body weight in the static upright position) [36], [38]. Although not significant, a reduction in TUG time from approximately 10 seconds to 6 seconds suggests a meaningful gain, given that the MCID for TUG ranges from 0.2 to 5.3 seconds depending on the GMFCS level.

The improvements observed in this study align with, and in some cases extend, those reported in prior neurorehabilitation studies for children with CP, including both conventional and technology-assisted interventions. Notably, the statistically significant improvement in the Box and Block Test (BBT) observed in our cohort is consistent with effects found in upper limb therapy programs such as constraint-induced movement therapy or goal-directed training [3], as well as in non-immersive VR interventions using EMG biofeedback [26]. These results suggest that the immersive VR approach can effectively stimulate the sensorimotor pathways required for grasping and releasing tasks.

C. Instrumental Observations

Subjects showed adaptation to the serious games, recording an overall increase of game-specific performance. Whenever the recorded performance did not increase, it was accompanied by an increase in the difficulty of the game parameters, meaning a similar indirect improvement in the game skills.

In the Potions Scenario, considering the parameters set by the clinical personnel, an evident push towards more challenging sessions is shown looking at the differences in distributions between start and end values (Fig. 7, Workspace Level). A statistically significant increase of Pouring Velocity can be noticed too, directly affecting the Completion Time and showing more confidence in the task, also marked by the trend of the fallen objects metric (not-significant). Also, it has to be noted a narrowing of the distribution quartiles for Pouring Precision and Pouring Angle, indicating steady parameters for children starting with the higher values, and gradually increasing parameters for the others.

Regarding the Spells Scenario, except for the Symbol Dimension the parameters set by the therapists have been changed to be more challenging for the participants (in particular, the Symbol Level and the Target Velocity). About the Symbol Dimension, an increase of the variance occurs without a difference in the median, possibly due to the needs of specific clinical cases: a bigger or smaller symbol can train either toward a wider workspace or a higher precision. Tracing Smoothness increased in a statistically significant way, showing an improvement of the quality of movement of participants while keeping the Tracing Velocity steady throughout the therapy. Aiming Error decreases until the mid of the therapy, then it increases due to the introduction of moving enemies in the game.

Similar trends of the parameters were found in the Eagle Ride scenario, making the game increasingly more difficult, in particular for the Speed Level and the Pitch Enabled parameters. Still considering the increased difficulty, participants obtained better performance throughout the therapy for the Heading Error and Velocity, revealing a higher confidence in the game and precision in the trunk motion.

D. Limitations

Although acceptability and engagement was particularly high especially at the beginning, from qualitative comments of the therapists, we noted that the initial enthusiasm tended to

wane over the longer rehabilitation period as the novelty wore off. Engagement lasted longer with the younger participants (about 6 to 10 years old). While the developed scenarios offered varied exercises and experiences, they are still far from the depth, complexity and longevity found in contemporary video game products. Also, targeting the gaming content to a wide range of ages in the developmental age is therefore another challenging, yet relevant, point to address.

In order to more accurately assess the effectiveness of the proposed methodology, a larger clinical study including a control group will be necessary. Furthermore, the serious games developed in this study are particularly suitable for children up to 8-9 years of age. This is partly due to the limited implemented game's complexity, perhaps less engaging for older children or adolescents who are used to commercial video games with more sophisticated contents and game mechanics.

Also, the use of a headset with a significant mass (503 g for the Meta Quest 2) might encounter additional limitations not emerged in the relatively small group of 12 children participating in this study. In example, head control problems (not found in the enrolled group) might be investigated in future studies as a possible exclusion criteria.

E. Conclusion

The proposed approach based on rehabilitation in immersive VR and serious games, supported by the technological improvements provided by the recent VR headsets, showed to be feasible to be adopted in a prolonged clinical study. Main advantages are found in the increased robustness and simplicity of the VR setup, in the adaptable exercises, and probably in the engaging gaming contents, obtaining high acceptability results. No adverse events were recorded, and all the included participants completed the treatment.

To this end, the developed game logic and parametrization proved effective to adapt the exercise to the participants, without creating blocking conditions. The measured constant game performance in certain metrics, when evaluated in the corresponding increased difficulty level of the parameters, showed that the therapist could actively control and adapt the difficulty of the game. Data analysis of the clinical scales shows an overall improvement of the participants' clinical outcome, with generalization of the motor skills acquired in the gaming exercises. The lack of a control group in the study does not allow a direct comparison with alternative rehabilitation approaches.

The use of immersive VR serious games was found to positively influence the engagement, as noted by direct therapist observations and supported by results of the acceptability questionnaire. This was found especially for the younger participants, while the appeal in the longer period was more limited for the others. Extension of the game longevity and complexity, here noticeably limited if compared to commercial video games, and targeting the content to a narrower range of ages can improve this point. The presented methods show also premises for potential use in home-based rehabilitation, due to the simple setup, low hardware cost, and continuous data recording. Yet, adequate supervision is still required

and the adopted technology, together with the developed exercise logic, would need a significant development on this direction.

REFERENCES

- [1] D. R. Patel, D. E. Greydanus, H. A. Omar, and J. Merrick, *Neurodevelopmental Disabilities: Clinical Care for Children and Young Adults*. Cham, Switzerland: Springer, 2011.
- [2] C. Morris, "Definition and classification of cerebral palsy: A historical perspective," *Develop. Med. Child Neurol.*, vol. 49, pp. 3–7, Feb. 2007.
- [3] L. Sakzewski, J. Ziviani, and R. N. Boyd, "Efficacy of upper limb therapies for unilateral cerebral palsy: A meta-analysis," *Pediatrics*, vol. 133, no. 1, pp. e175–e204, Jan. 2014.
- [4] L. Sakzewski, R. Boyd, and J. Ziviani, "Clinimetric properties of participation measures for 5-to 13-year-old children with cerebral palsy: A systematic review," *Develop. Med. Child Neurol.*, vol. 49, no. 3, pp. 232–240, Mar. 2007.
- [5] K. L. Collins et al., "A review of current theories and treatments for phantom limb pain," *J. Clin. Invest.*, vol. 128, no. 6, pp. 2168–2176, Jun. 2018.
- [6] S. J. Ackerley, W. D. Byblow, P. A. Barber, H. MacDonald, A. McIntyre-Robinson, and C. M. Stinear, "Primed physical therapy enhances recovery of upper limb function in chronic stroke patients," *Neurorehabilitation Neural Repair*, vol. 30, no. 4, pp. 339–348, May 2016.
- [7] K. Nas, L. Yazmalar, V. Şah, A. Aydin, and K. Öneş, "Rehabilitation of spinal cord injuries," *World J. Orthopedics*, vol. 6, no. 1, p. 8, 2015.
- [8] R. M. Maura, S. R. Parra, R. E. Stevens, D. L. Weeks, E. T. Wolbrecht, and J. C. Perry, "Literature review of stroke assessment for upper-extremity physical function via EEG, EMG, kinematic, and kinetic measurements and their reliability," *J. NeuroEng. Rehabil.*, vol. 20, no. 1, p. 21, Feb. 2023.
- [9] R. Colombo et al., "Robotic techniques for upper limb evaluation and rehabilitation of stroke patients," *IEEE Trans. Neural Syst. Rehabil. Eng.*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 311–324, Sep. 2005.
- [10] N. Aderinto, G. Olatunji, M. O. Abdulbasit, M. Edun, G. Aboderin, and E. Egbunu, "Exploring the efficacy of virtual reality-based rehabilitation in stroke: A narrative review of current evidence," *Ann. Med.*, vol. 55, no. 2, Dec. 2023, Art. no. 2285907.
- [11] W.-S. Kim et al., "Clinical application of virtual reality for upper limb motor rehabilitation in stroke: Review of technologies and clinical evidence," *J. Clin. Med.*, vol. 9, no. 10, p. 3369, Oct. 2020.
- [12] S. Burin-Chu, H. Baillet, P. Leconte, L. Lejeune, R. Thouvarecq, and N. Benguigui, "Effectiveness of virtual reality interventions of the upper limb in children and young adults with cerebral palsy: A systematic review with meta-analysis," *Clin. Rehabil.*, vol. 38, no. 1, pp. 15–33, Jan. 2024.
- [13] M. J. Fu, A. Curby, R. Suder, B. Katholi, and J. S. Knutson, "Home-based functional electrical stimulation-assisted hand therapy video games for children with hemiplegia: Development and proof-of-concept," *IEEE Trans. Neural Syst. Rehabil. Eng.*, vol. 28, no. 6, pp. 1461–1470, Jun. 2020.
- [14] L. Wang, J.-L. Chen, A. M. K. Wong, K.-C. Liang, and K. C. Tseng, "Game-based virtual reality system for upper limb rehabilitation after stroke in a clinical environment: Systematic review and meta-analysis," *Games Health J.*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 277–297, Oct. 2022.
- [15] G. King et al., "The nature, value, and experience of engagement in pediatric rehabilitation: Perspectives of youth, caregivers, and service providers," *Develop. Neurorehabilitation*, vol. 23, no. 1, pp. 18–30, Jan. 2020.
- [16] S. Demain, C. D. Metcalf, G. V. Merrett, D. Zheng, and S. Cunningham, "A narrative review on haptic devices: Relating the physiology and psychophysical properties of the hand to devices for rehabilitation in central nervous system disorders," *Disab. Rehabil., Assistive Technol.*, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 181–189, May 2013.
- [17] J. Zhang et al., "TouchMark: Partial tactile feedback design for upper limb rehabilitation in virtual reality," *IEEE Trans. Vis. Comput. Graphics*, vol. 30, no. 11, pp. 7430–7440, Nov. 2024.
- [18] E. F. Borja, D. A. Lara, W. X. Quevedo, and V. H. Andaluz, "Haptic stimulation glove for fine motor rehabilitation in virtual reality environments," in *Proc. Augmented Reality*, Otranto, Italy, Jun. 2018, pp. 211–229.
- [19] A. L. Martin-Niedecken and U. Götz, "Go with the dual flow: Evaluating the psychophysiological adaptive fitness game environment 'plunder planet,'" in *Proc. Serious Games, 3rd Joint Int. Conf.*, Valencia, Spain, Nov. 2017, pp. 32–43.
- [20] A. V. Zakharov, V. A. Bulanov, E. V. Khivintseva, A. V. Kolsanov, Y. V. Bushkova, and G. E. Ivanova, "Stroke affected lower limbs rehabilitation combining virtual reality with tactile feedback," *Frontiers Robot. AI*, vol. 7, p. 81, Jul. 2020.
- [21] I. Bortone et al., "Immersive virtual environments and wearable haptic devices in rehabilitation of children with neuromotor impairments: A single-blind randomized controlled crossover pilot study," *J. NeuroEng. Rehabil.*, vol. 17, no. 1, pp. 1–14, Dec. 2020.
- [22] C. Camardella, M. Gabardi, A. Frisoli, and D. Leonardis, "Wearable haptics in a modern VR rehabilitation system: Design comparison for usability and engagement," in *Proc. Int. Conf. Hum. Haptic Sens. Touch Enabled Comput. Appl.*, 2022, pp. 274–282.
- [23] C. Camardella, D. Chiaradia, I. Bortone, A. Frisoli, and D. Leonardis, "Introducing wearable haptics for rendering velocity feedback in VR serious games for neuro-rehabilitation of children," *Frontiers Virtual Reality*, vol. 3, Jan. 2023, Art. no. 1019302.
- [24] M. Ceradini, E. Losanno, S. Micera, A. Bandini, and S. Orlandi, "Immersive VR for upper-extremity rehabilitation in patients with neurological disorders: A scoping review," *J. NeuroEng. Rehabil.*, vol. 21, no. 1, p. 75, May 2024.
- [25] J. W. Yoo, D. R. Lee, Y. J. Sim, J. H. You, and C. J. Kim, "Effects of innovative virtual reality game and EMG biofeedback on neuromotor control in cerebral palsy," *Bio-Med. Mater. Eng.*, vol. 24, no. 6, pp. 3613–3618, Nov. 2014.
- [26] J. W. Yoo, D. R. Lee, Y. J. Cha, and S. H. You, "Augmented effects of EMG biofeedback interfaced with virtual reality on neuromuscular control and movement coordination during reaching in children with cerebral palsy," *NeuroRehabilitation*, vol. 40, no. 2, pp. 175–185, Mar. 2017.
- [27] A. T. Booth, A. I. Buizer, J. Harlaar, F. Steenbrink, and M. M. van der Krogt, "Immediate effects of immersive biofeedback on gait in children with cerebral palsy," *Arch. Phys. Med. Rehabil.*, vol. 100, no. 4, pp. 598–605, Apr. 2019.
- [28] A. MacIntosh et al., "The design and evaluation of electromyography and inertial biofeedback in hand motor therapy gaming," *Assistive Technol.*, vol. 34, no. 2, pp. 213–221, Mar. 2022.
- [29] I. Bortone et al., "Wearable haptics and immersive virtual reality rehabilitation training in children with neuromotor impairments," *IEEE Trans. Neural Syst. Rehabil. Eng.*, vol. 26, no. 7, pp. 1469–1478, Jul. 2018.
- [30] J. Y. Choi et al., "Virtual reality rehabilitation in children with brain injury: A randomized controlled trial," *Develop. Med. Child Neurol.*, vol. 63, no. 4, pp. 480–487, Apr. 2021.
- [31] Y. G. Jung, H. J. Chang, E. S. Jo, and D. H. Kim, "The effect of a horse-riding simulator with virtual reality on gross motor function and body composition of children with cerebral palsy: Preliminary study," *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 8, p. 2903, Apr. 2022.
- [32] S. L. Pavão, J. L. B. Arnoni, A. K. C. D. Oliveira, and N. A. C. F. Rocha, "Impact of a virtual reality-based intervention on motor performance and balance of a child with cerebral palsy: A case study," *Revista Paulista de Pediatria*, vol. 32, no. 4, pp. 389–394, Dec. 2014.
- [33] K.-J. Liang, H.-L. Chen, J.-Y. Shieh, and T.-N. Wang, "Measurement properties of the box and block test in children with unilateral cerebral palsy," *Sci. Rep.*, vol. 11, no. 1, p. 20955, Oct. 2021.
- [34] G. Moreno-Morente, M. Hurtado-Pomares, and M. C. T. Cantero, "Bibliometric analysis of research on the use of the nine hole peg test," *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health*, vol. 19, no. 16, p. 10080, Aug. 2022.
- [35] R. D. Nicolini-Panisson and M. V. F. Donadio, "Timed 'up & go' test in children and adolescents," *Revista Paulista de Pediatria*, vol. 31, no. 3, pp. 377–383, 2013.
- [36] T.-N. Wang, K.-J. Liang, Y.-C. Liu, J.-Y. Shieh, and H.-L. Chen, "Psychometric and clinimetric properties of the Melbourne assessment 2 in children with cerebral palsy," *Arch. Phys. Med. Rehabil.*, vol. 98, no. 9, pp. 1836–1841, Sep. 2017.
- [37] H. Carey, K. Martin, S. Combs-Miller, and J. C. Heathcock, "Reliability and responsiveness of the timed up and go test in children with cerebral palsy," *Pediatric Phys. Therapy*, vol. 28, no. 4, pp. 401–408, 2016.
- [38] Y. Chen, H. D. Fanchiang, and A. Howard, "Effectiveness of virtual reality in children with cerebral palsy: A systematic review and meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials," *Phys. Therapy*, vol. 98, no. 1, pp. 63–77, Jan. 2018.